

INNOVATIVE METHODS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract:

This article examines the use of innovative methods in the teaching of foreign languages at the Institute of Foreign Languages, Moscow City Teachers' Training University. Highlighting the shift from traditional to modern educational tactics, the study delves into the impact of these methods on enhancing the efficacy of language education. It discusses the integration of communicative language teaching and web-based learning into curricula, reflecting on how these approaches cater to the evolving needs of students in a globalized context.

Key words: Methods, Approach, New devices, ICT, learning process, Communicative language teaching. Web based learning.

doi: <https://doi.org/10.2024/n2dwoh86>

Basically, teaching must include two major components sending and receiving information. Ultimately, a teacher tries his best to impart knowledge as the way he understood it. The use of innovative methods in educational institutions has the potential not only to improve education, but also to empower people, strengthen governance and galvanize the effort to achieve the human development goal for the country. With a number of educational options available before the present generation learners, the newer trends seem to have emerged in the field of education that have entirely changed the face of traditional system of education. Recent trends, methodologies and developments portray the vital role of education sector in general with its internalization of the education process, stress on quality above quantity, increase in the adoption of technologies, necessity for professional talent etc. English language teaching has undergone tremendous changes over the years, especially the last ten years. Students are burdened with studying, learning and grasping the materials, and of course, lectures with the collections of relevant information from prescribed texts. Many career alternatives once regarded insignificant are gaining importance at present such as communication skills, soft skills, technical skills, interpersonal skills, ICT literacy etc. For this, a change in the trend especially the teaching learning process of English language has to undergo a transition for the betterment. Seasons change, fashions change, attitudes of human beings change but it is important to note that in the last century English curriculum has hardly undergone any change. There had been much of changes in the attitude of people as to what they perceive to be a language. Rigid curriculums and huge syllabi continue to threaten students who speak regional dialect but love to excel in English. The history of foreign language has always been an important practical concern. It was Latin which dominates various fields like education, commerce, religion and government in the western world. In 16th Century French, Italian and English achieve lot of importance as result of political changes in Europe. As the status of Latin

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language from that of living language to teaching subject in school curriculum. According to Elley and Warwick “The study of classical Latin and analysis of its grammar becomes the model from foreign languages study from 17th to 19th century. In 21st century we are going to teach communicative language teaching” [3,238]. Communication is the groundwork based on which any idea can progress and develop into a fully one. Without that, sustenance in any field is impossible. During the last decade, various crucial factors have combined to affect the current ideologies of teaching of English such as the ineffective methodologies, unsuitable materials, and integration of contextualized teaching, over emphasis on multi language skills etc. Teachers who practiced Grammar Translation method during the previous decade solely relied on black board as the apt tool to impart communication skills and the nuances of English language. Later on, over-head projectors, acted as another medium for the teacher dominated class room. Such teachers believed in the dictum of drill and practice. Researchers had given more emphasis on authentic and meaningful contextualized discourse. Then they focused on a successful adult second language learning as a parallel process to a child’s first language acquisition. With the advent of e-communication, it has been made possible for the English language teachers to enrich their profession. Basically, the teacher controls the instructional process, the content is delivered to the entire class and the teacher tends to emphasize factual knowledge. In other words, the teachers deliver the lecture content and the students listen to the lecture. Thus, the learning mode trends to be passive and the learners play little part in their learning process. It has been found in most universities by many teachers and students that the conventional lecture approach in classroom is of limited effectiveness in both teaching and learning. This method had stayed in practice for a good period of time due to its focus on the functional use of English. But, it needed a lot of time, good budget and a small class size. And even in some situations, it was not very useful. These issues led to another method that is called Audio-Lingual Method. Maley claimed that “The Direct method is natural method of teaching foreign language its makes use of Audio-Visual Aids. The direct method originated in France in 1801. The direct method develops as a reaction against GTM. Its basic principle is that pupils should think directly in foreign language” [4,98]. DM is to teach language directly at aims to create direct bond between the word and meaning, thought and expression. It’s also improving the pupil’s pronunciation. In 21st century there is a rise of communicative methodology which emphasizes real meaning communication method than activity, topic and situations which are artificial and remote from pupil’s lies. The process of English communication learning will be more student-centered but less time consuming. Therefore, it promises that the teaching quality will be improved and students’ applied English communication can be effectively cultivated, meaning that students’ communicative competence will be further developed. Language in education would ideally and ordinarily build on such naturally acquired language ability, enriching it through the development of literacy into an instrument for abstract thought and the acquisition of academic knowledge. Teachers use a range of local texts or English translation of literature in the classroom. The use of language as well as the use of a variety of accents in listening activities or tests is encouraged in the English language classroom. With the proliferation of tablets and smart phones, it is believed that textbooks will disappear in a few years. Furthermore, the access to knowledge in terms of flexibility and mobility has changed drastically. Teaching in English language classes focuses on fostering the students thinking as well as language content, outcomes and learning activities. There are significant and complex student-teacher interactions inside and outside the classroom. In a knowledge-based society and to remain competitive and employable, teachers are expected to engage in a continuous professional development or the professional learning activities from the

International Conference

ADVANCED METHODS OF ENSURING QUALITY OF EDUCATION: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

beginning to the end of their careers. As with any other profession, teachers are also expected to assume a greater responsibility for their own professional learning, continually developing their knowledge and skills. Having realized the need of the hour: English teachers convene different types of conferences and seminars to create a platform and to get to know the upcoming ideologies in the ELT and also to upgrade themselves professionally. It is the fifth skills of language that enables the efficiency to use grammatical structures with accuracy. Academic qualification alone may not help teachers to grow professionally, on the other hand, they need to be equipped themselves with the current practices. The teaching materials that are being used in our country are almost made available all over the world. There had been too many methodologies of teaching English language. The third dimension of globalization which is inseparable from English teaching is an advancement of Information and According to Damon and Phelps, "Communicative language teaching (CLT) emphasizes on the process of communication rather than the mastery of language. Sometimes the term functional approach is use for communicative approach or communicative method" [2,11].

Web based learning is one of the fastest developing areas. There are thousands of English web-based classes that offer trainings for a variety of basic language skills such as Learning, Speaking, Reading and Writing and are made interactive in a variety of ways. Some of the common technologies are available for promotion of education are as follows: The students can correspond with native speakers of the target language using an e-mail by creating a personal e-mail account (g-mail, yahoo, etc.) which is free. The students can mail their home work to the teachers concerned and get it corrected in turn. The teacher can also provide revisions, feedback, suggestions for the betterment of every work and send them back. Every internet service has audio functions, and technological instruments like laptops with cameras. The students could communicate with their teachers and friends who are far away. Likewise, they could very well communicate with the speakers of native language and get their pronunciation checked so as to improve their speaking. Learners can search for new words using dictionary option in the mobile phones and enrich their vocabulary. They may verify the spelling pronunciations and usage of the specific word they searched for. Across the world, information technology is dramatically altering the way student; faculty and staff learn and work. As the demand for technology continues to rise, colleges and universities are moving all sorts of student services, from laundry monitoring to delivery online. Technology is also changing the classroom experience. In addition, tablet PCs, compact computer that allow you to write notes directly onto the screen with a special pen, replace the archaic projector. With the tablet technology allow professor to make notes on charts and spreadsheets and send them directly to their student's PCs. The traditional method lays more emphasis on a teacher himself and is teacher centered. Repetitive practice, mechanical drills and memorization are the hallmarks of the traditional methods. Role of the teacher is to pertain to the long cherished traditional notion that pedagogic principles depend on how articulately a teacher teaches. It is imperative to understand the current trends and evaluative methods of the ELT. The researchers believe that the objective of teaching is passing on the information or knowledge to the minds of the students. Any method using computers or modifying the existing conventional chalk-talk method are innovative if they ultimately serve the attainment of core objective of teaching.

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